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University of Alberta Simplified Template (Funding Application Stage) - Mixed Methods Research Example

A Data Management Plan created with DMP Assistant

Data Management Planning Expert Group

Information

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Template: University of Alberta Simplified Template (Funding Application Stage)

Project abstract: This fictional data management plan (DMP) example focuses on mixed methods research (survey & interviews and focus groups) using the *University of Alberta Simplified Template (Funding Application Stage)* template within the [DMP Assistant](#) tool. The U of A simplified template was created based on the *Alliance Simplified Template (Funding Application Stage)* template developed by the DMP Expert group, designed specifically to assist researchers in meeting DMP requirements at the funding application stage. This DMP example was developed by Ceri MacMillan (DMP Specialist, University of Alberta Library) and James Doiron (Research Data Management Strategies Director, University of Alberta Library; Co-chair, Digital Research Alliance of Canada DMP Expert Group) for educational and guidance purposes. As DMPs are context driven and vary in scope, some DMPs may require more or less detail than what is provided in this example. A related and more detailed example DMP based on the same project and using the *Alliance Template for Mixed Methods (Surveys & Qualitative Research)* is available within the Alliance's [Zenodo](#) collection.

The premise of the project is that the study topic of interest is not sensitive in nature, does not include any Indigenous communities or knowledges, and that participants have provided informed consent for the de-identified information collected from them to be deposited for long-term preservation, discoverability, and open access.

Including an abstract that provides an overview of your research project will assist readers and/or reviewers of your data management plan (DMP) in understanding your project, including its purpose, focus, and goals, and the associated DMP.

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Guidance

In light of the introductory guidance provided, if there are any related points of consideration with respect to your proposed research project and which will help with the development of your DMP in the following Question section, you may initially capture them here.

When using acronyms within your DMP (Data Management Plan), it is recommended to spell them out at least once within any given category so that readers understand what the acronym is referring to.

The introductory guidance provided with respect to funder/institutional requirements, guiding best practice principles, Indigenous data governance, and roles and responsibilities for managing the research data was very helpful. We have considered these all applicable, and this is reflected in the details of our data management plan and the larger funding application.

Questions

What considerations will you take into account with respect to ethical, legal, or commercial issues?

Describe any applicable ethical, legal, or commercial considerations related to your project and data. This includes research involving Indigenous communities and knowledges, human subjects, legal and commercial considerations/agreements, partnerships or data with a high level of risk associated with it.

Our research data will follow the legal and ethical policies set out by the University of Alberta Research Ethics Board. Data will be stored in Canada and upon project completion will be retained for a 5-year minimum. We do not anticipate the research data to include any sensitive topics, involve Indigenous communities and knowledges, or have commercial implications. Data deposit and secondary usage will be clearly explained to participants, and informed consent will determine any data usage restrictions. Ideally, de-identified data will be openly discoverable and accessible via the University of Alberta Borealis - Dataverse repository, supporting data deposit requirements.

What data will you collect or otherwise bring into your project under this plan?

Describe the data that will be collected, generated, and/or acquired.

Consider estimating as early as possible how much data, and what types of data you will be collecting as this can help you gain a sense of how much storage space you require both during the active phase of your research project, as well as to support the long-term stewardship of your data, including with respect to data deposit and preservation.

Data collected will consist of project data, survey data, semi-structured interviews and focus groups. We estimate collecting 200 surveys, 30 interviews (~30 min in length each), and 3 focus groups (~90 min in length each). Magnitude of data, accounting for file versions (raw, master, analytic) is estimated to be under 16 GB. Other accompanying documentation, including transcriptions and project management is estimated to require 2 GB of storage. Estimated total storage requirements: 18 GB.

Project data includes identity lists of participants, working documents and other project work. The research data collected will produce tabular data, video audio, and text-based data (including transcriptions for all interviews and focus groups). Survey data will be collected using REDCap software and will be anonymous, with no direct or indirect identifiers present. Qualitative interviews will be conducted using virtual recordings over Zoom.

File formats will exist in both non-proprietary and proprietary formats. Survey data will exist in .csv, MS Excel, & SPSS formats, and for sharing and long-term access will be in .csv format. Interview & focus group data will exist in .mp4, MS Word & NVivo formats. Final de-identified versions of the interviews and focus groups transcripts will be exported into a basic text format (.txt) for deposit, and long-term preservation and access.

How will you document data for future re-use or validation?

Describe how you will document your data to ensure that it is easily read and interpreted correctly throughout the research process. If applicable, specify any data and/or metadata standards that are being used to support your research project.

Where and to the degree appropriate, consider how your project and data are able to embrace the FAIR Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable). <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

Metadata documentation protocols will be developed prior to starting data collection - these will clearly detail expectations, standards, and processes for capturing and implementing documentation to support the project. Protocols will notably encompass file naming conventions, file versioning, folder structure, and both descriptive and structural metadata. Project staff and researchers will undergo training regarding these processes. There will be a dedicated lead role for ensuring documentation and metadata standards used are consistently updated according to policies and procedures.

REDCap provides a data dictionary outlining codes and variables as well as time and date stamps and other key information. After consulting with the metadata team within the University of Alberta Library, we concluded that the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) metadata standard, which REDCap employs, will optimally support our survey data.

Qualitative research data, including digital audio-visual files and the corresponding verbatim transcriptions, will be named and versioned. Copies of the master transcripts will be created and used for analysis purposes. It's not yet determined which metadata standards will be used for supporting qualitative research, but the team will consult with on-campus expertise to determine if there are any standards that can be used.

Qualitative interview transcripts will include summary information including name of data collector, location of interview, and the date and time that the interview was conducted and will also have accompanying notes containing key contextual information and metadata. Documentation explaining naming conventions, metadata standards chosen, software used throughout the project, and any processes for accessing these data will also be created and updated as needed throughout the project, and final anonymized copies will accompany any data destined for long-term preservation and access.

How will data be stored, accessed and worked with?

Describe both where and how data will be stored, accessed, and worked with during the *active phases* of your research including as applicable:

- **all versions of data (e.g., raw, master, analytic)**
- **All activities (e.g., data collection, processing, analysis, dissemination)**
- **All software and platforms**
- **Who requires access, including security measures (e.g., Investigators, research staff, collaborators, partners)**
- **How data will be backed up to prevent data loss**

Data storage and backup procedures will be clearly outlined within the project's data collection policies and procedures and made accessible by all researchers and staff.

Data will be securely stored on the Digital Research Alliance of Canada's (DRAC) cloud platform and will be accessible only by approved researchers, trainees, and project staff. Access to the platform is securely password protected, with access rights approved by the PI. Researchers can access this VRE (Virtual Research Environment) remotely, along with software required. This VRE has a regularly established scheduled backup process in place to ensure no data loss occurs.

File names will include, as needed: file version (raw, edit, master, analytic), date (i.e., dd/mm/yyyy), and applicable key contextual information, (e.g., geographical location, interviewer initials, version number or code). These protocols will be implemented to support the active phases of the research project.

Upon export from REDCap, survey data will be named as 'raw' data and transferred using a FTP (File Transfer Protocol) process to the VRE. REDCap servers are hosted by WCHRI (Women and Children's Health Research Institute) within the Faculty of Medicine and Dentistry at the University of Alberta and undergo regular backups. There may be some additional versions between the raw and final data as needed. Final and processed data will be named and versioned as 'master' data. From the master survey data, a variety of analytic data files may be created, each adhering to the file naming convention. When converting survey data between formats there will be systematic checks - both case and variable wise - to ensure that no data is lost.

Upon completion of the interviews, data will be securely transferred within 48 hours to the project's VRE. Interviews, once uploaded, will be permanently deleted from the local computers on which they were saved.

Video interview participants will be de-identified, referring to them by codes or pseudonyms, with a participant key stored separately from the rest of the data. There will be no video component to the video files, as participants are not required to turn on cameras, therefore only the audio will be saved. Any other potentially identifiable information shall be removed. Verbatim transcriptions will be saved and versioned as a 'raw' transcript, with no contextual information removed. Raw transcripts will be provided to the interviewer to review for completeness and to remove any necessary indirect identifiers from the text that may have been missed. Once this has occurred it will be named and versioned as a 'master' transcript. Information about the transcription process, including the names of the transcribers, will be stored and available upon request from the research team.

How will data be managed, discoverable, and accessible for the long term?

Describe plans for long-term management of your data after the active phases of your research have concluded including data deposit and sharing.

Consider and describe as applicable plans for:

- **all versions of data deposited (raw, master, analytic, published)**
- **All activities (e.g., curation, preservation, ethical compliance, publishing, etc.)**
- **All software and platforms (e.g., data repositories)**

It is important to think ahead and identify how your data will be effectively managed, including who will be involved in their management. Not all projects have the same needs but, to varying degrees, most require dedicated time, capacity, and resources to help effectively manage the data across the research lifecycle.

We will use the University of Alberta's instance of Borealis, the Canadian Dataverse Repository to deposit and support long-term preservation, discovery, and access of the research data. For long-term storage and preservation, we will preserve both raw and master (cleaned, processed and de-identified) versions of the surveys, and only the approved and de-identified interview and focus group transcripts. The data available for sharing will be in non-proprietary formats to promote accessibility and re-use of the data and contact information for the project leaders will be listed for any additional access requests or questions.

The research team will obtain participant consent to share the data and will be depositing and making available an example of our study information letter, participant consent form, as well our approved institutional ethics application.

Restrictions requested by participants will be considered. All data will fall under open data licensing (CC-BY 4.0), unless any changes occur during the data collection stage of the research project which necessitates changing the type of end-user license.

